

A New Hope for Network Model Generalization

CRediT Statement

11 October 2022

This document lists the author's contributions to the following work. The contributions are described using CRediT, the Contributor Roles Taxonomy, an ANSI/NISO standard. All authors agree with this declaration of contributions.

Title A New Hope for Network Model Generalization

DOI 10.1145/3563766.3564104

Alexander Dietmüller	0000-0003-3769-3958	
Conceptualization	Equal	
Data curation	Supporting	
Investigation	Supporting	
Methodology	Lead	
Project administration	Equal	
Software	Supporting	
Supervision	Equal	
Visualization	Lead	
Writing – original draft	Equal	
Writing – review & editing	Equal	

Siddhant Ray	0000-0003-0265-2144	
Data curation	Lead	
Investigation	Lead	
Methodology	Supporting	
Software	Lead	
Validation	Lead	
Visualization	Supporting	
Writing – review & editing	Supporting	

10.5281/zenodo.7189024

Romain Jacob	0000-0002-2218-5750	
Conceptualization	Equal	=
Investigation	Supporting	
Methodology	Supporting	
Project administration	Equal	=
Supervision	Equal	=
Visualization	Supporting	
Writing – original draft	Equal	=
Writing – review & editing	Equal	=
Laurent Vanbever	0000-0003-1455-4381	
Conceptualization	Supporting	
Funding acquisition	Lead	
Investigation	Supporting	
Methodology	Supporting	
Project administration	Supporting	
Resources	Lead	
Supervision	Supporting	
Writing – original draft	Supporting	
Writing – review & editing	Supporting	